

THE ARTISTIC CREATION AND LIFE OF ALEXANDER FEINBERG

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13729329>

Abstract:

The article describes the life journey of Alexander Fainberg, an outstanding poet, highlighting the challenges and joyful moments from his birth until his passing. Special attention is given to his attachment to Uzbekistan, the Uzbek people, and the poets and writers of this country. Despite the obstacles and hardships in his life, Fainberg's passion for literature never waned, and through his talent, he became a renowned and recognized figure.

Keywords:

Literature, compilations, feature films, Uzbek tea houses, translations, poet.

Literature is a bridge that unites nations and strengthens the bonds of friendship. Although works are written in different languages, they reach the hearts of people. Indeed, the language of literature is one — the language of art. Throughout the history of literature, there have been creators who, despite being representatives of other nations, have sung the sorrows and spirit of the Uzbek people and contributed significantly to promoting our literature to the world. One such writer is Alexander Fainberg, a holder of the Pushkin Medal. Without a doubt, he is one of the brightest stars in the sky of Uzbek poets. For instance, Uzbekistan's National Poet, Abdulla Oripov, the author of the national anthem of Uzbekistan, expressed his thoughts about Fainberg: "When it comes to Alexander Fainberg's work, all lofty words do not even reflect one percent of reality because he was truly a unique poet and translator. No writer who speaks Russian can sincerely sing songs about our sunny land."

Uzbekistan's People's Poet Alexander Arkadyevich Fainberg was born on November 2, 1939, in Tashkent. His parents moved from Novosibirsk two years before his birth, in 1937. He spent his childhood on the former Zhukovsky Street. After completing seven years of school, Fainberg entered the Tashkent Topographic Technical School. Upon graduating from the technical school, he went to serve in the military in Tajikistan. He then graduated from the correspondence journalism department of Tashkent University (now Tashkent State National University).

Alexander Fainberg is the author of fifteen poetry collections. He has written compilations such as «Bicycle Tracks», «Etude», «Sonia», «Poems», «Distant Bridges», «Seal of the Sky», «Response», «Short Waves», «The Waver of Time» and «Free Sonets.» Additionally, his poems have been published in magazines such as “Смена” («Change»), “Юность” («Youth»), “НОВЫЙ МИР” («New World»), “Звезда Востока” («Star of the East»), “Новая Волга” («New Wave»), as well as in the press of foreign countries like the USA, Canada, and Israel.

Fainberg has also made significant contributions to cinema. In total, he has authored seven film screenplays, four of which are feature films. Based on his screenplays, films such as «My Brother», «Under the Blazing Sun», «Those Who Were Trapped in Qandahar», and «Under the Deep Blue Sky» were shot at the “O‘zbekfilm” studio, while the “Tojikfilm” studio produced «The Criminal and the Defenders» and other films.

In 1999, on the 12th anniversary of the tragic plane crash involving the «Pakhtakor» football team, a film titled «Stadium in the Sky» was made based on his screenplay. The song featured in the film was written by Alexander Fainberg in 1979. Additionally, around 20 animated films have been created based on his screenplays.

Fainberg's poetry is characterized by a vibrant humor. In his epic «Rubai Tor,» he depicts the unchanging dish of Uzbek tea houses in such a way that it cannot be read without a smile on one's face. In his poetic works, the past intertwines with the present, the West with the East, and national identity with internationalism, creating a unique artistic world. The lyrical hero of Fainberg's poetry retains his human essence amidst historical and social upheaval, ready to extend a hand of compassion and assistance to others while also suffering from the unpleasant events occurring around the globe.

Fainberg's poetic creativity harmonizes the finest artistic experiences of Russian and European poets. The traditions of Eastern classical poetry are also integral to his creative style. The poet's work is prolific and extensive. His poems shine with diversity, philosophical depth, clarity of emotions, and vividness. He deeply feels words, inviting readers to share in this experience. He lived and created in Uzbekistan, where the air, sky, soil, people—indeed, the entirety of this land—are as precious to him as poetry itself.

The profound passion and talent of the great poet for literature made it a vital part of his existence. As the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, remarked, «Literature is the soul of the nation; it embodies the spirit of the people. In challenging times, we must connect with the human heart, harnessing

literature's influence for noble purposes. We honor and study the legacies of our ancestors, fostering an environment for the creation of literature that reflects our cultural values.»

Alexander Fainberg dedicated himself to exploring the poetic and artistic contributions of Uzbeks. His translations played a crucial role in introducing the remarkable works of Uzbek poets to Russian audiences. Fainberg was instrumental in promoting Uzbek poetry by translating notable pieces, including the epic works of Alisher Navoi and other distinguished poets. In Moscow, he translated Otakir Hashimov's «The Uprising of Spirits» and poetry collections by Abdulla Oripov.

In one of his essays, he expressed, «I wear happiness on my forehead. I live in an independent Uzbekistan... I have received significant support from Uzbek writers like Abdulla Oripov and Erkin Vahidov throughout my literary journey. Writers, artists, musicians, and other creatives have shown me great kindness.» He regarded himself as a son of Uzbekistan and cherished his life in the country until his passing just shy of 70 in Tashkent, where he found love. In recognition of his contributions to Uzbek literature and his esteemed place among Uzbeks, annual events are held in Uzbekistan to honor Alexander Fainberg..

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